

EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT (ESD) PROGRAM TO BUILD CHARACTER AT IGM AL-IHSANIYAH ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOL GANDUS PALEMBANG

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Abstract

This study aims to describe the implementation of the Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) program and its supporting and inhibiting factors at the IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School. This type of research is a case study with a qualitative approach. The research participants were the principal, curriculum coordinator, permaculture, fine arts, food education teachers, Person in Charge (PIC) of the internship and mangrove planting program, students of the IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School. Data collection techniques with observation, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis techniques with data condensation, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. Test the validity of the data with triangulation of techniques and sources. Results of the study: ESD at the IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School is integrated into subjects and activities. Program implementation: communication through integrated socialization in learning activities, human resources are competent, human resources are needed in accordance with the scientific field for permaculture, budget resources and facilities are available and adequate, permaculture still needs to be fulfilled, program disposition gets a positive response from all school residents, bureaucratic structure is attached to the school organizational structure. Supporting factors: support from various parties, good coordination and collaboration, budget resources and facilities, schools value students more. Inhibiting factors: pandemic conditions, human resources for environmental ESD are not yet in accordance with the scientific field, permaculture subject facilities are not complete, weather obstacles, internship program supervisors have not fully supervised students.

Keywords: Implementation, Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), Building Character, Sustainable Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Achieving educational goals is an important social aspect in the context of national development. The idea of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) was born from the issues of environmental crisis and humanitarian issues faced today and future challenges. The concept of ESD in Indonesia as Sustainable Development Education, was initiated by the United Nations under the United Nations

Education, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). ESD is organized for relevant education that places responsibility for the future as the main focus (UNESCO, 2020).

The principle of ESD encourages holistic learning with innovative learning models, is flexible, adapts to local contexts, and can be through learning programs or in the form of any action. Research by Lauri et al (2016) in eighteen countries shows that ESD contributes to improving quality education in the primary (SD) and secondary (SMP) education sectors. The importance of ESD was also presented in the National Workshop on the Indonesian Initiative Towards Sustainable Education in 2030 held by the Ministry of Education and Culture through the Indonesian National Commission for UNESCO on April 6, 2021.

The results of the Puslitjaknov evaluation show that the implementation of ESD in Indonesia has not been optimally implemented, one of the reasons being that there is no explicit reference for implementation from the government and minimal socialization (Suprastowo, 2010). The principle of ESD in Indonesia is in accordance with the education system contained in the 2003 National Education System Law and the 2013 curriculum. At the beginning of its implementation, ESD was included in the 2010-2014 Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Education (KNIU, 2014). Regulations regarding ESD are contained in the Memorandum of Understanding on the Development of Environmental Education. Sustainable development in Indonesia has been formulated in Presidential Regulation Number 59 of 2017 concerning the Implementation of Achieving Sustainable Development Goals. The education sector is listed in the fourth goal out of a total of 17 goals. ESD is a key supporter of achieving each goal in the SDGs action plan and as a key element in the field of education (UNESCO, 2020)

An educational approach with sustainable principles is needed to educate generations to be able to meet their needs without having to risk the ability of future generations to meet their needs. There are three basic pillars in the ESD concept, namely environmental sustainability, economic progress, and socio-cultural aspects of society (Syakur, 2017). These three aspects are integrated because these pillars are core aspects of various issues and problems faced globally by humans. ESD is currently an integral element in the sustainable development action plan or Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) whose target is until 2030 (UNESCO, 2020).

It is clear that ESD is important in supporting the environmental care and culture movement in schools, playing a role in raising awareness and developing individuals, especially students, to make decisions and actions that are responsible for the environment, community welfare and economic sustainability both now and in the future. This is stated in the SDGs. The role of education is important as a means of changing the way individuals and communities think and act with sustainable values. The direction of education needs to create a peaceful and sustainable world for the survival and prosperity of society. ESD provides knowledge, skills, values, attitudes, and behaviors to empower each student to be responsible and have integrity in preserving the environment, economic sustainability, respecting cultural diversity, and community empowerment. IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School is a school that applies the ESD concept and participates in realizing the sustainable development action plan or SDGs in implementing education. The principles in ESD are in line with the philosophical values of the City of Palembang, which include Sustainable Development

II. THEORY AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The meaning of Implementation according to is understanding what actually happens after a program is declared valid or formulated is the focus of attention of policy implementation, namely events and activities that arise after the ratification of state policy guidelines, which include both efforts to administer them and to cause real consequences/impacts on society or events Arief (2014). Policy

implementation is limited to reaching actions taken by government individuals and private individuals (groups) that are directed to achieve the goals that have been set in previous policy decisions (Abdullah and Yudi, 2016). The beginning of the emergence of ESD (Education for Sustainable Development) was from environmental education which became a global issue at the time of the United Nations (UN) conference. The conference discussed the Human Environment in Stockholm, Sweden, 1972, becoming a driving force for humans to focus attention on environmental problems. At the next conference, the global community emphasized the need for interrelation between the environment and socio-economic issues, both concerning poverty and underdevelopment in development. Since the 1980s, the concept of sustainable development has grown as a response to the need to balance economic and social progress with attention to the environment and preservation of natural resources, and continued at the conference A decade later (1992) the UN held "The World Summit on Sustainable Development" which was held in Johannesburg, 193 countries and 58 international organizations participated. Finally it was decided to reaffirm the results of the meeting in Rio De Janeiro (Eco-92) in the form of commitments related to interdependence in economic growth, social justice, and environmental protection. The main goal is to eradicate poverty, change unsustainable patterns in producing, consuming existing natural resources (Soares, et al., 2011).

Figure 1: Concept Model

The concept of sustainable development was first introduced in 1987 by the World Commission on Environment and Development (Brundtland Commission) through its book *Our Common Future*. It was in this book that the term sustainable development was introduced. According to the Brundtland Report in the World Commission on Environment and Development (1987), sustainable development is a development process based on the principle of "meeting the needs of the present generation without sacrificing the ability of the future to meet theirs". In other words, development is essential to meeting human needs and improving the quality of human life. There are three perspectives in ESD which are its main pillars, namely:

- a) Socio-cultural, namely related to issues of human rights, peace and human security, gender equality, understanding of cultural and intercultural diversity, health, HIV & AIDS, and governance
- b) Environmental, namely related to issues of natural resources (water, energy, agriculture, biodiversity), climate change, rural development, sustainable urbanization, disaster prevention and mitigation
- c) Economic, namely related to issues of poverty reduction, corporate responsibility, accountability and reorientation of the market economy.

Based on these three perspectives, it can be seen that there is a relationship between aspects that cannot be separated from each other in supporting ESD. This means that in the implementation of ESD, one cannot prioritize only one aspect but must pay attention to all three aspects, namely socio-cultural, economic, and environmental.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study type of research, observing and knowing the phenomena needed to achieve the research objectives. This research was conducted at the IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School in October 2023. The research subjects were taken using a purposive sampling technique to select authorized subjects, become implementers and are directly involved in the program implementation process. The subjects consisted of the principal, curriculum coordinator, teachers, program PIC, and students, this selection was based on the research objectives (Moleong, L.J., 2011; Creswell, 2014; Hamidi, 2018)

The data collection techniques used in this study were observation, interviews, and documentation. The research instrument used supporting instruments, namely, observation guidelines, interviews, and documentation. The data analysis technique used the interactive model of Miles, Huberman, and Saldana (2020), namely data condensation, data presentation, and drawing conclusions/verification. Data validity test is used to avoid researcher subjectivity, so this study uses technical and source triangulation. Source triangulation is done by comparing interview results from research participants/subjects, while technical triangulation is done by checking observation results, interviews, and documentation (Suharsimi, 2015; Sugiyono, 2018).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School applies the values of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) in organizing education, although it does not directly state that the school is ESD-based. ESD values are integrated into its vision, mission and curriculum. This is in accordance with the statement of the Coordinating Minister for Human Development and Culture Puan Maharani at the 2018 UNESCO session which stated that the implementation of ESD in Indonesia is integrated into the 2013 curriculum with special attention to character development, poverty reduction, entrepreneurship, health, gender equality, and environmental sustainability (Djojonegoro, et al., 2020). In this study, the implementation of the program was realized in the form of intracurricular activities (several subjects) included in group B/local content, two of which were formulated according to their own characteristics and in the form of school activity programs.

The concept of ESD at the IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School is a learning that encourages school residents, especially students, with a learning process that supports sustainable development. Aimed at providing knowledge, skills, and attitudes so that all school residents have the ability to encourage the sustainability of sustainable future development and become a school effort in realizing the SDGs. This goal is in accordance with the UNESCO statement (2017) that as an integral key element in achieving SDGs in goal 4, the ESD paradigm provides individuals with the knowledge and competence to realize each point of all sustainable development goals that represent the urgency of the economic, socio-cultural, and environmental fields.

Figure 2: Vision, Mission and Objectives of IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Supporting ESD and Sustainable Development

The implementation of the vision and mission that includes ESD values is derived into several forms of programs, the three pillars of ESD are integrated into subjects, especially how learning is carried out by providing an understanding of caring for, preserving the environment, and properly caring for school natural resources with agricultural activities. This is in accordance with the theory in (Aisy & Gunansyah, 2020:2), the application of environmental aspects that include conservation activities and awareness of the main functions of the ecosystem, social aspects that strengthen the nature of humans as social beings and community cooperation and economic aspects are the use of natural resources wisely. The social pillar is manifested in the value of habituating students to contribute and work together to carry out agricultural activities. Students learn to meet food needs with permaculture, but still cannot plant everything alone, for example to plant rice. The value is to introduce the role of students in society, that humans as social beings cannot work alone, but need to participate. Then in the economic pillar, students are taught to have skills in meeting food needs economically and begin to participate in supporting the government's food security program. therefore, in the economic aspect, permaculture is an effort to use natural resources wisely.

The integration of ESD values in this subject is done by minimizing the use of media and materials that are not environmentally friendly such as styrofoam, plastic, and toxic paint to create works. The use of these media is allowed if they are recycled. Many works of art utilize unused items such as used cardboard from school computer packaging. Several other works of art are also made from natural materials, such as leftover tea, leftover paper, and materials found around the school such as leaves, roots, flour, and clay. These materials are used for coloring, batik stamping tools, ecoprint batik, making clay works, key chains, solid sculptures, and so on. The environmental pillar is inserted through

the value of caring for the environment by not using non-biodegradable materials, but recycling and using natural and environmentally friendly media in creating works. This is in accordance with Tristinanda's statement (2018: 42-29), the environmental pillar is carried out with awareness of the impact of human activities and environmental protection efforts. In the social aspect, children do not turn a blind eye to issues that occur in society. Students also voice their sensitivity to environmental issues through artworks that are full of messages at the school exhibition. In that way, students also contribute indirectly. For the economic pillar, this subject also teaches that every artwork has economic value. The results of students' work assignments can be sold in a fundraising/business day activity to buy mangrove seeds, returning to action for the environment.

Initially, the school delivered the program through a growth session for new teachers facilitated by CSIE, one of the divisions. Communication of ESD programs for prospective students needs to be communicated from the start by including it in brochures and on the website. After officially becoming new students, holding a growth session in the series of MPLS agendas for socializing ESD values does not hold special socialization about ESD, but each value and principle in ESD has been clearly integrated. Socialization is carried out through instilling and habituating the ESD values contained in each program, for example concern and the role of caring for the environment, respecting diversity among others, tolerance, or independence in entrepreneurship. Socialization is also obtained through assemblies (ceremony) with certain issues and themes conveyed by the students themselves. Physical/written socialization through posters or slogans attached is also not widely found. Other socialization is carried out in other ways and opportunities, such as inviting resource persons/experts as speakers, for example through webinars with related themes that also have several regulations such as the prohibition of plastic and the obligation to bring eating and drinking utensils as well as a school culture that does implement inclusive and multicultural education. This includes one of the habituation efforts to instill behavior to appreciate diversity. School residents still have various interpretations regarding the definition of ESD because socialization is not carried out by providing an understanding of what the definition of ESD itself is, but more on the values, intent, and objectives of ESD that are instilled in each program. Overall, teachers and students are able to interpret the intent and values of ESD well. Students as the main target of socialization have also understood the values, objectives, and what needs to be done to implement ESD through the school programs that are being carried out.

IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School has the availability of competent and skilled human resources, both because of their educational background that is in accordance with their field of knowledge and expertise. As an inclusive school, it is also open to the interests and passions of teachers outside their field of knowledge, so it facilitates it by providing training. At IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School there is no special personnel selection. The recruitment process is carried out according to needs and fields of knowledge. IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School does not have a special team to implement the ESD program. Providing incentives in Edward III's theory is a recommended technique to influence implementers to carry out their duties properly. There are no special incentives given to teachers. Because the implementation of this program has been integrated into the hours of teaching and learning activities (JP) and is not carried out outside school hours.

One of the characteristics of ESD is its interdisciplinary nature, no discipline can claim ESD alone but all disciplines can contribute (UNESCO, 2005:30-31). In addition, the ESD criteria of KNIU (2014:11-13) state that ESD is interdisciplinary and holistic. Interdisciplinary Unit (IDU) is a learning approach that collaborates several subjects by matching the same basic competencies (KD) to become a project. These projects can be in the form of videos, films, posters, infographics, and so on. IDU is routinely used in the implementation of Mid-Semester Assessments (PTS) and in daily learning. With the

Interdisciplinary Unit, students do a lot of project-based learning. In general, environmental aspects are indeed applied more, but are still balanced with connections that are not separated from socio-cultural and economic aspects. The three pillars/aspects are interrelated, not standing alone. In addition to learning activities, supported by the implementation of inclusive and multicultural education, so that a culture and habituation are created in dealing with differences, understanding others, being fair, and respecting others. In the building concept, especially in the classrooms in the form of joglo limasan, some of the wooden material elements are from recycled wood. In addition, there is a security post in the form of a cow shed. This is an effort by the school to implement environmental sustainability values.

5. CONCLUSION

Implementation of the Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) Program at the IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School In the process of implementing the Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) program, communication was carried out well through socialization. The school community was able to understand the values, intent, and objectives of ESD well even though the understanding of the definition was still diverse. The Human Resources (staff) of the IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School were competent and skilled in carrying out their duties. The IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic Boarding School developed and improved the competence and interests of its human resources through training, enrichment, and webinars during the pandemic. The main budget resources came from the foundation and have been met according to needs. Facility resources have been available and the condition of the facilities is quite good, for some facilities are still in the stage of being fulfilled, especially permaculture subjects. The authority resources are held by the IGM Al-Ihsaniyah Gandus Palembang Islamic. Disposition of the implementer, each program with a positive response. The selection of personnel is carried out evenly, there is no special team to implement ESD, the recruitment process is according to needs. The selection of the person in charge of the Person in Charge (PIC) activity is carried out ad hoc. There are no special incentives because the incentive is the teacher's salary given according to teaching hours (JP). The bureaucratic structure in implementing the ESD program is attached to the school's organizational structure. In the implementation of the program, especially the communication aspect, its socialization can be strengthened again by conveying about ESD so that every teacher and student has the same understanding and meaning to achieve the goal of building character that supports Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) for sustainable development.

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